

Installation and Data Acquisition from a Real Time Air Quality Sensor (RTAQS) Monitoring Pilot Breathing Air

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ABBREVIATIONS

GC/MS	Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry
TD	Thermal desorption
OBOGS	Onboard oxygen generation system

ABSTRACT

This study revolved around the flight testing of a sensor suite built to address the need for detection elements to protect United States Air Force pilots. A set of gaseous sensors specific to O₂, CO₂, CO, NO_x species, and hydrocarbons both laboratory and flight testing. Additionally, thermal desorption (TD) tube was collected for contaminant discovery through gas chromatography mass spectrometry analysis. Thirty-two sorties were flown. Of the sensors O₂, CO, and CO₂ returned measurable values. Overall, both the sensor readings and the TD tube sampling were successful in monitoring the breathing air supplied to the pilot.

INTRODUCTION

An increase in fighter jet pilot physiologic incidences over the past ten years has warranted the request for a system to monitor the breathing air produced onboard. Air crew approaching mass media outlets with reports of physiological events has highlighted

the need to address the current deficiencies in sensing capabilities. From a forensic standpoint no system exists to eliminate potential causative factors of these events. To respond to this increased frequency of incidence the United States Air Force (USAF) assembled a team of specialists to identify a potential cause(s). The team consisted of 711th HPW/USAFSAM military, civilians, and contractors focusing on collecting samples of breathing air along with sensing from the breathing line in real time. The 711th collaborative group worked to assess the effectiveness of already existing technology. Ultimately a collaboration between the 711th, NASA Glenn Research Center (GRC), and Makel Engineering materialized to leverage developing gas sensor technologies. The direct interface between 711th and Makel engineering lead to a prototype known as the Real Time Air Quality Sensor (RTAQS) that included sensors specific to O₂, CO₂, CO, NO_x species, and hydrocarbons paired with a TD tube sampling system. This prototype was tested in the exposure chamber, and its performance evaluated against “real world” pressure and contaminant events. Eventual collaboration with the Test Pilot School of Edwards Air Force Base created a rare opportunity to install the device on a two-seat training F-16.

METHODS

The RTAQS was installed in an altitude chamber where the concentration of O₂ was increased to 50% and run through a profile of stepped altitudes up to 20,000 ft equivalent pressure. For the remainder of the sensors MultiRAE standard gasses were fed through to confirm positive response and functionality.

Edwards’ engineers with the Test Pilot School converted a map case to an envelope to install the RTAQS unit. In addition, they designed a specialized lid that would allow flight line personnel to access the communications port for data download, and the top mounted TD tube for replacement on a per flight basis. While TD tubes were replaced for each flight, larger data downloads from the sensors’ logger occurred at two-week intervals. Those data were then provided to the 711th HPW along with the coordinated flight integrity data for overlay.

Figure 1 — Programmed versus observed pressures and O₂ concentrations. The figures above compare the expected pressures (A) versus the observed line pressures (B). Also, based on the expected O₂ concentration (C) we can determine how well the observed adheres to the set profile (D).

Figure 2 — Flight profiles compared against O₂ and CO concentration. Relationships between spikes in both O₂ (A-green) and CO (B-orange) appear synchronous with rapid ascents and descents as recorded throughout the flight.

Figure 3 — Carbon monoxide plotted against the absolute vertical acceleration. During analysis it was found that G load (black) and O₂ variation were predictive correlates of the appearance of CO spikes (orange).

Figure 4 — Correlative model suggesting it's possible to predict occurrence of a CO spike based on O₂ and G-load.

TD tubes returned to the 711th were loaded onto a TD auto sampler and analyzed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS). The EPA method TO-17 was used to identify a set of 65 specified compounds. While concentrations were derived for each, they were not valid as the sample volume acquired to each tube exceeded the calibrated volume of the GC/MS system.

All data were then analyzed by an in-house statistician looking for relationships between the sensor readings of the RTAQS and the data taken from the jet's in-flight characteristics.

RESULTS

Thirty-two (32) sorties were completed with the unit installed on the aircraft. Of those 32-sensor data was successfully acquired from a total of 20. Due to operator failure to power up the system sensor data was not collected from the remaining 12. Of the 20 successful, ten had accompanying flight integrity data downloaded directly from the jets' onboard computer. Thermal desorption tubes were successfully collected in 16 of the sorties where sensor data was acquired.

Aggregate graphs of both the pressure in the breathing line, and the O₂ concentration supplied to the pilot

Figure 5 — Chromatographic data from TD-Tubes collected during the test sortie. For each sortie a passive “background” sample (blue) accompanied the flight tube (green) to control for non-flight exposures. In certain cases, the unit was not powered up and thus did not collect to the TD tube. There is an observable difference between the blank and flight tube for the “Pump on Sortie”, but negligible intensity difference for the “Pump off Sortie”.

Figure 6 — Difference between flight tubes and blank tubes with regards to enrichment of compounds collected to TD-Tube. It should be noted that TD tubes associated with flights where the unit was not powered on by flight crews are similar to their “background” counterpart in the fold change of the total ion chromatogram.

showed relative agreement between the published programmed values,¹ and the observed values (Figure 1). In a small portion of sorties the O₂ levels reached the 90th percentile (possibly dictated by the “maximum mode” of the OBOGS). Breathing line pressure also traced the flight profile (Figure 2). Minor oscillations occurred in the O₂ readings that synchronized with changes in the absolute altitude of the jet. Carbon monoxide readings were also correlative with changes in G-load and vertical acceleration (Figure 3 and Figure 4). After GC/MS analysis direct comparisons were made between the flight TD tube and its accompanying “background” tube to confirm anything was collected (Figure 5 and Figure 6).

CONCLUSIONS

This was the first flight testing of a combination sensor suite and sampling media. While these data are interesting with regards to the O₂, CO, and sampled

contaminants it is difficult to draw direct conclusions with regards to the OBOGS performance. It should be noted that the F-16 flown for the duration of this study was a non-incident aircraft, and that no physiological events took place throughout the study. Only one CO spike exceeded the set TWA (50 ppm) values with 50.2 ppm. This spike lasted a matter of seconds while the TWA values are derived from constant exposure for an eight-hour work day.

Instead, these data can be treated as a training set for future test sorties. By increasing the N for test sorties the focus would be placed on three major points discussed above. First, pressure and O₂ would continue to be directly compared to the programmed expected values of the airframe. This would differ depending on the jet type, but would still be regulated based on the engineered specifications. Second, the same correlations between CO and the jet's flight profile would be tested to answer the following questions: 1) is there a repeatable spike in CO with increasing G-load or ascent/descent, and 2) are the same variables correlative in different aircraft or must a separate model be built? Finally, we've identified a list of compounds from the TD tubes collected to base future sensor development on. These compounds are all EPA method TO-17 compounds and quantifiable under the right sampling regime. We were unable to quantify for this test due to the lack of control over the sampling time, but for future reference, steps have been taken to reduce the flow rate over the tube and provide a functional sampling volume.

References

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